

ISic3682

I.Sicily inscription 3682

Language

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

7km from Siracusa, near the Siracusa/Noto road, in the area called
'Milocca' or 'Matrensa', a hypogeum in predio Gallitto (37.02434,
15.26701)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi(?)

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 357-358 no.1

Bechtel, F., Collitz, H., Meister, R. C., Bezenberger, A. 1884-1915. Sammlung der griechischen Dialekt-Inschriften. Göttingen. At 5244a

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